

When space rules time: the Kappa effect with concurrent visual and tactile stimulation

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The spatial and temporal dimensions of a subjective experience are intertwined. In the Kappa effect, the spatial distance between consecutive visual stimuli proportionally influences the perceived duration of the inter-stimulus interval. Despite its relevance, to our knowledge no study has investigated such an illusory effect in concurrent multimodal perception through visual and tactile elicitations. To overcome this limitation, we characterise the Kappa effect on vision and somatosensation also through the assessment of duration perception in the sub-second range when sensory inputs are delivered on the palm or forearm using wearable devices. The effect of unimodal visual/tactile elicitations was also compared to several bimodal stimulations. Results showed that the illusory effect, which arose in both unimodal conditions, produces significantly higher distortions in vision. In the multimodal condition, when visual stimuli were at non-equidistant spatial locations, the integration with the tactile channel did not diminish the Kappa effect. Conversely, the Kappa effect vanished when the visual stimuli were at equidistant spatial locations, independently from the tactile stimuli location. These findings shed light on the human perceptual mechanisms, suggesting that perceptual channel with lower variance in the spatial discrimination has a preeminent role in determining illusory perceptions in the time domain.

1. Introduction

There are clear inter-dependencies in the perception of time and space in humans [1, 2], and a paradigmatic example is the so called *Kappa effect*, where the duration of the time interval between two or more consecutive stimuli is influenced by their physical distance. In particular, the perception of isochrony is modulated by space, and the greater the spatial distance between stimuli, the longer the duration is perceived, and vice-versa [2].

In the visual domain, the Kappa effect has been demonstrated by several authors [2–4] through different experimental protocols. In the auditory domain, a pitch space modeling was proposed to account for the Kappa effect [5]. A Kappa effect was also found in a stereophonic scenario, where inter-stimulus time (IST) was perceived longer when it was generated along different directions (i.e., right-left or left-right) than when it was generated on the same direction (i.e. left-left or right-right) [6]. In the tactile domain, the evidence of the Kappa effect has been seldom reported: Suto [7] induced a Kappa illusion by providing consecutive tactile stimuli alternately on the forearms: participants were required to hold the forearms crossed each other, therefore perceiving different apparent spatial distances between tactile stimuli.

More recently, Grondin *et al.* [8] found that the consecutive stimulation on different hands (i.e., left-right or right-left) was perceived longer than stimulations on the same hand (i.e., right-right or left-left). However, partially in contrast with [7], the increase in physical distance between the hands did not affect the perceived duration. Yoblick *et al.* [5] found no relation between the frequency of the tactile vibration and the perception of the duration. Finally, to the best of our knowledge, no studies reported a consistent Kappa effect in the tactile domain on the same body site (e.g., the forearm, the palm): speculatively, as suggested by Goldreich [9], this might be due to the poor spatial accuracy of the body site tested compared to the distance of the stimuli provided (i.e., skin stimulation areas within the two-point-discrimination threshold).

The Kappa effect elicited by the multiple modalities has received scarce attention. Bausenhardt *et al.* [10] found a significant Kappa effect originated by a visual stimulus on the estimation of auditory interval duration. The same authors were able to generate a time dilation by modulating the asynchrony between visual and auditory stimuli [11]. Interestingly, the delivery of auditory stimuli produced a quasi-optimal temporal integration in the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) sense when the attention of participants was focused on the visual domain; the Just Noticeable Difference (JND) was significantly lower in the bimodal condition than in the unimodal visual condition confirming that the perceptual channel having the lower variance in the time domain, i.e. audition, has a greater influence in the cross-modal integration process [12].

Despite its relevance in the neuroscience of human perception, to the best of our knowledge no studies have investigated the illusory Kappa effect in vision and somatosensation. In our former preliminary study, the interaction between the visual (V) and tactile (T) domains for the elicitation of the Kappa effect has been investigated in the forearm through visuo-tactile stimuli [13]. Here, we comprehensively characterize the link between time perception and multimodal visual-tactile conditions, also through psychometric functions, within the peripersonal space (PPS) (i.e., at the palm and the forearm). PPS is known to enhance the effects played by the stimuli with neutral valence that are used in psychophysics (e.g., light flashes, tactile taps) [14].

More specifically, we provide a systematic psychophysics modeling of the Kappa effect in the visual-tactile domain. As shown in Fig. 1, for each factor (and combinations thereof) we fitted individual psychometric functions by evaluating seven complementary IST. Combined factors included the spatial distributions of stimuli, the modality (i.e. visual (V), tactile (T), bimodal congruent (BC), bimodal incongruent visual (BIV) and bimodal incongruent tactile (BIT)) and the body site (i.e., forearm and palm). Besides testing the presence of the Kappa effect with multiple combination of IST with different duration, this study investigates the Kappa effect elicited by bimodal stimulation with congruent or incongruent spatial information to provide a

thorough characterisation of the effects of the visual-tactile crossmodal integration concerning the temporal [11] and the spatial [12] domains for the elicitation of the Kappa effect. Humans are able to integrate congruent visual and tactile information in a statistically optimal fashion [12], however, when the stimuli are not congruent (i.e., not interpreted as a unique percept), the brain may apply different integration or segregation strategies to optimize the statistical inference [15, 16]. Finally, our analysis investigates the dependency between the magnitude of the Kappa effect and the temporal discrimination thresholds of each participant.

2. Methods

(a) Participants

Fifteen right-handed participants (10 males and 5 females, $M=31.7$, $SD=5.9$) took part in the experiment. They participated on a voluntary basis and were not paid. Each participant reported normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity and no sensorimotor impairments. Informed consent was obtained prior to participation. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the University of Pisa (Prot. n. 36590/2021).

(b) Hardware

Figure 2: Wearable devices used in the experiment. Left: forearm device exemplifying the stimuli sequences short(S) and long(L), right: palm device reporting the field of view perceived at a distance of 30 cm.

We designed two wearable devices, which can deliver tactile and visual stimuli to the forearm and the palm. Figure 2 shows the schematics of forearm and palm devices, having a size of $200 \times 22 \times 35mm$ ($L \times W \times H$) and $88 \times 22 \times 35mm$, respectively. Each device provided five consecutive, evenly spaced stimulation points whose distance was selected with respect to the two-point-discrimination tactile thresholds (i.e., $42mm$ forearm and $14mm$ palm [17]).

Furthermore, each device provided a visual fixation point placed at the center, at a distance of $24mm$ perpendicularly to the stimulation direction (participants

Figure 1: left: the factors combinations (Space, Modality, Place) tested in the experiment. Right: the expected Kappa effect reported in three representative psychometric curves, which results in a shift of the point of subjective equality (PSE) in the S (contraction of the perceived temporal distance between stimuli) and L (dilation of the perceived temporal distance between stimuli) spatial conditions with respect to the PSE in the control condition (C). The psychometric curves were evaluated across seven complementary IST having increasing duration differences of 60 ms.

were asked to look at the fixation point during each trial). The tactile stimuli were delivered by 5V push-pull solenoids driven by independent power circuits [18]. The visual stimuli were delivered through a series of WS2812 LEDs (white color) whose positions were in correspondence with those of the solenoids. The onset time and the duration of the stimuli were controlled by an Arduino Mega 2560 microcontroller connected to a laptop PC running Matlab R2021a (MatLab Inc., USA). To ensure a precise temporal control of the stimuli, each trial of the experiment was managed by the microcontroller timers. Temporal synchronization and stimuli duration were measured by comparing the microcontroller digital output signal of the LEDs with the recordings of a ADXL327Z accelerometer on repeated measurements. Maximum time mismatch was always under 1.2ms.

(c) Stimuli and procedure

The experiment followed a within-subject design: all participants tested all factor combinations of space, IST, modality and place. The experiment was divided into two sessions sharing the same procedure, one for the forearm and one for the palm. The order of the sessions was counterbalanced across participants. Sessions were interleaved by 7 to 10 days.

The experiment adopted a widely used experimental procedure [1, 19] that provides the observer with three consecutive stimuli (E1, E2, E3), designed to define two successive temporal intervals (T^1, T^2) and two contiguous spatial intervals (S^1, S^2), see Fig. 1 and 2. Independently from the space existing between the stimuli, the observer was asked to compare the duration of the two temporal intervals following a two-alternative forced-choice (2AFC) protocol.

In each trial of the experiment, three successive stimuli (E1, E2, E3) either visual (V), tactile (T) or visual-tactile (VT), were delivered to the forearm or to the palm depending on the session. The duration of the stimuli was 47ms [3, 4]. The total time $T = T^1 + T^2$ between the first (E1) and the third (E3) stimulus was always equal to 600ms; within each session, also the total space $S = S^1 + S^2$ between the first (E1) and the third (E3) stimulus was constant: 56mm for the palm, and 170mm for the forearm, respectively [9, 20]. Instead, the spatial intervals $S^1 = S_{E2-E1}$ and $S^2 = S_{E3-E2}$ were variable [2]. Figure 1 shows the possible combinations of complementary spatial intervals presented to the observers given equal time intervals lasting 300ms each: the trials conveying the Kappa effect provided different spatial intervals ($S^1 \neq S^2$) having a ratio between the first and the second interval of 1/3 (Short) or 3/1 (Long). Conversely, the trials conveying the Control condition provided equal spatial intervals ($S^1 = S^2$).

According to the 2AFC protocol, seven combination of IST $T^1 = T_{E2-E1}$, and $T^2 = T_{E3-E2}$ with increasing differences were provided to the observer, see Fig. 1; in one combination the IST was the same, and equal to 300ms. The minimum difference between temporal intervals was selected to be 60ms from the literature about the gap detection on visual and tactile modalities [21], and the maximum difference was selected to be 180ms, to ensure a sufficient discrimination in both the modalities [22]. Each of the seven time intervals was repeated 20 times for each factor combination.

Trials were grouped in 13 blocks sharing the factor Modality (i.e., V, T, VT). Within each block 140 trials were fully randomized. Both the unimodal conditions V and T provided the observer with: 3 space ratios \times 7 time intervals \times 20 repetitions = 420 trials. In the bimodal condition (VT) stimuli were always synchronized in time. Regarding the space, instead, the VT condition provided also incongruent

trials where one perceptual channel provided the Kappa effect, whereas the other channel provided the control condition (i.e., equal space intervals). Therefore, in the bimodal conditions there were: 420 congruent trials (BC), same as in unimodal condition, plus 280 incongruent tactile trials (BIT), in which visual stimuli were delivered to identify two spatially equivalent intervals - control condition ($S_{visual}^1 = S_{visual}^2$) and the tactile stimuli were delivered to identify two different spatial intervals (either S or L condition) ($S_{tactile}^1 \neq S_{tactile}^2$), plus further 280 incongruent visual conditions (BIV), as the inverse of the latter ($S_{visual}^1 \neq S_{visual}^2, S_{tactile}^1 = S_{tactile}^2$). Since the direction of the stimuli sequence was proven to not affect the Kappa effect [2, 4], it was set constant for each device: left-to-right on the palm, bottom-up on the forearm. Therefore, in total each participant performed 1820 trials for each session, 3640 in total.

The experiments took place in a quiet room. Figure 3 shows an observer wearing one of the experimental devices fastened to the non-dominant hand (according to the literature [23], the multi-sensory integration is enhanced in the non-dominant hand). Participants were asked to place their arm on the support (tilt 60°) keeping their forehead on the headrest by adjusting the height of the chair: this way the distance between the eyes and the LEDs on the devices was kept constant at 30cm. As a reference, Fig. 2 reports also the 8° Field Of View (FOV) from the fixation point at a distance of 30cm, the area where the visual Kappa effect was found at its maximum extent [4].

Figure 3: Setup of the experiment.

During the experiment, participants wore ear-plugs while a continuous pink noise (approximately 70dBA) was delivered through earphones to mask any parasitic noise produced by the solenoids. Each experimental block was started by an LCD screen showing the next modality (i.e., V, T, VT) to the participant. In each trial, participants had to choose the *shortest time interval* pressing the left or the right arrows on a keyboard placed nearby the arm support. The next trial started 700 – 900 ms after a response was recorded.

Before the experiment, to familiarize with the experimental procedure, participants performed a training phase of 48 trials on all the modalities with time intervals of

150ms and 450ms, respectively. The experimenter checked that participants were able to distinguish the two intervals and that they clearly understood the task. Participants were allowed to rest between blocks as their convenience. A typical session lasted 1.5 hours.

For each participant, several data were collected and processed anonymously: age, gender, use of glasses, arm length, forearm length, palm length, palm width, experience with professional dance, experience in playing musical instruments. Participants signed a written consent form and were identified by a coded number used in both the experimental sessions.

3. Results

For each participant, the responses of the 2AFC discrimination task were modeled as a psychometric function for each factor combination of place (forearm, palm), space covered by the first interval (short, equal, long, corresponding to S, C, L condition, respectively) and modality (i.e., V, T, BC, BIV, BIT) by fitting a cumulative Gaussian function with two free parameters: midpoint μ , and standard deviation σ . Given such parameters, it was possible to estimate the two main variables of standard psychophysical analysis: the point of subjective equality (PSE) as the midpoint, and the just notable difference (JND), calculated as $\sqrt{2} * \sigma^2$.

The parameters of the psychometric functions fitted for each participant were used in the statistical analysis. Since the individual distributions of PSE and JND were not normally distributed (i.e. D'Agostino normality tests were [24]), non-parametric group-wise Friedman tests for paired samples [25] were performed. Therefore, whether significant differences emerged, post-hoc pairwise comparisons were performed using non-parametric Wilcoxon test for paired samples with Holm correction [26]. A further modeling of the Kappa effect by means of generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) can be found in the Appendix. Data were analysed using the software R 4.1.2 using *Quickpsy* [27] and *MixedPsy* [28] packages.

Figure 4 reports the overall psychometric functions calculated for all combinations of place, space, and modality factors grouped by participants, at a group-wise level. The PSE of the psychometric functions increases or decreases due to the space factor according to the Kappa effect: longer spatial intervals result in time dilation and viceversa. Of note, a larger PSE corresponds to a shorter perceived duration of the first interval, while the PSE is close to zero in all the control conditions with equally-spaced intervals (red lines in Fig. 4) independently from the modality and place factors. A PSE close to zero in the control condition accounted for a correct temporal discrimination of equidistant stimuli, therefore confirming the absence of systematic biases in determining the longest time interval.

Figure 4: Psychometric functions calculated at the population level for all factor combination

(a) Kappa effect

For each participant, Friedman's test on the PSE revealed highly significant differences across the space factor (i.e. $p < .0001$) for each combination of modality and place, except for the BIT modality ($p < .05$). The differences among PSE were confirmed by a post-hoc pairwise comparison, showing $PSE_{long} < PSE_{equal}$, $PSE_{equal} < PSE_{short}$ and $PSE_{long} < PSE_{short}$ according to the Kappa effect (all p-values $< .01$).

We computed the difference between the PSEs in the short (S) and long (L) spatial intervals to quantify the magnitude of the Kappa effect. This, in turn, provides an overall estimation of the perceptual alteration induced by different spatial distribution of isosynchronous stimuli.

Figure 5 illustrates the boxplots of the magnitude of the Kappa effect at all modalities in the forearm and the palm. Regarding the forearm, the Friedman test for paired samples showed significant differences among modalities ($Q = 29.4$, $p < .0001$). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons for paired samples with Holm correction revealed significant differences between visual and tactile modalities ($p < .05$) and between visual and BIT modalities ($p < .05$). Regarding the palm, the Friedman test showed significant differences among modalities ($Q = 33.7$, $p < .0001$). Again, the post-hoc pairwise comparisons revealed significant differences between visual and tactile modalities ($p < .05$) between visual and BIT modalities ($p < .05$).

Figure 5: Magnitude of the Kappa effect for all factor combinations of Modality and Place

(b) Duration discrimination

The JND of the psychometric curves account for the participants' ability to discriminate the temporal duration of different intervals: the lower the JND, the higher the ability. Figure 6 and 7 shows the boxplot of the JND grouped by modality and space for the forearm and the palm, respectively. Separate Friedman tests were performed for

each factor. At all modalities, the factor Space was found not significant concerning both the palm and the forearm. Instead, the factor Modality was found significant only concerning the control condition, with equal intervals.

In the forearm, post-hoc comparisons revealed a statistically significant higher JND for the visual modality with respect to the tactile and the BC modalities ($p < .0167$); in the palm, differences were significant between the visual and the BC modality ($p < .0167$).

For each participant, the JNDs measured in visual and tactile modalities were used to estimate the expected discrimination thresholds in the BC modality following the MLE rules [29] (i.e., in multimodal conditions the discrimination threshold should be mainly influenced by the perceptual channel with the lower variance); these estimations were then compared with the experimental data.

Figure 6: JNDs of the psychometric functions for all modalities of the forearm

Figure 7: JNDs of the psychometric functions for all modalities of the palm

Figure 8: Forearm: discrimination thresholds in the BC modality vs. theoretical MLE thresholds. Optimal integration occurs for all the dots on the dashed lines.

Figure 9: Palm: discrimination thresholds in the BC modality vs. theoretical MLE thresholds. Optimal integration occurs for all the dots on the dashed lines.

Figures 8 and 9 show the thresholds measured in BC modality in the experiment with respect to the estimated optimal integration calculated from the unimodal thresholds for the forearm and the palm, respectively: the lower the distance from the dashed bisector, the higher the MLE integration. For low discrimination thresholds experimental values are in agreement with MLE estimation, while as the thresholds increase, the experimental data are higher than the theoretical estimated thresholds.

(c) Relation between Kappa effect and JND

Figure 10 reports the scatterplot of the magnitude of the Kappa effect as function of mean JND of individual participants calculated separately at each modality for the forearm and the palm, respectively. A Spearman's analysis between the magnitude of the Kappa effect and mean JND revealed significant correlations for the stimulation on the palm in visual $R = .89, p < .0001$, tactile $R = 0.88, p < .0001$, BC $R = 0.94, p < .0001$, and BIV $R = 0.90, p < .0001$, whereas for the stimulation on the forearm there were significant correlations in visual $R = 0.78, p < .001$, tactile $R = 0.80, p < .001$, BC $R = 0.88, p < .0001$, BIV $R = 0.85, p < .0001$, and BIT $R = 0.54, p < .05$;

Figure 10: Scatterplot of the magnitude of the Kappa effect as function of mean JND of each participant in the forearm (left) and the palm (right)

Figure 11: Relation between JND and magnitude of the Kappa effect. Each subplot shows the relation between JND and Kappa effect for all modalities (colors) and places (maker) of a participant. As a reference, each subplot reports also the linear dependency for the visual (red) and the tactile (gold) unimodal modalities depicted in Fig.10.

Figure 11 reports the scatterplots of the magnitude of the Kappa effect as function of mean JND of each participant for each Modality and Place.

(d) Static predictors

The subject-specific effects that results from the distributions of PSE and JND might be explained by the

static predictors that were recorded for each participant, namely age, gender, arm length, forearm length, palm length, palm width, use of glasses. We investigated whether the subject-specific Kappa effect was correlated with any of the static predictors for all modalities. The Kappa effect was found significantly higher in females than males in the tactile modality ($p = .03$). However, in all the other modalities the differences of gender were not significant ($p > .5$). Regarding the experience in music and dance, on one hand, musicians reported lower Kappa effect and lower JND than non musicians; on the other hand, participants with dance experience reported low JND than non-dancers. However, such differences were not statistically significant. All the other static predictors (i.e. age, arm length, forearm length, palm length, palm width, use of glasses) did not show any correlation with the Kappa effect or the JND.

4. Discussion

We demonstrate that perceptual illusions associated with the so-called Kappa effect may be elicited with specific, concurrent visual and tactile stimuli. Such perceptual illusions are associated with a high inter-subject variability especially in terms of the magnitude of the Kappa effect, which is defined as the difference between the PSE computed for the short (S) and long (L) spatial interval conditions. Building on previous evidence [2–4], our findings confirm the presence of the Kappa effect in visual and tactile domains, also in the PPS and within the same body site [9]. Moreover, differently from [7, 8], we characterised the Kappa effect in touch considering, for the first time, contiguous areas of the skin, i.e. on the palm and the forearm.

(a) Magnitude of Kappa effect

Considering the unimodal conditions, the magnitude of the Kappa effect was generally greater in vision than in touch ($p < .05$). In each trial of the experiment all the processing stages needed to compare time intervals were affected by the perceptual domains involved (i.e., visual and/or tactile) concerning both the spatial and temporal dimensions. Compared to previous studies, the stimulation protocol envisioned the delivery of visual and tactile stimuli to the same body site, thus enabling a comparison of the effects produced by these types of stimulation. As shown in figures 4 and 5, there are no statistically significant differences between the forearm and the arm in terms of the magnitude of the Kappa effect in the tactile domain. This finding can be explained by considering the choice of the spatial distance between the location of the tactile actuators used in the wearable devices. This distance was increased from 14 mm, in the wearable device for the palm, to 42 mm, in the wearable device for the forearm, which correspond to the two-point discrimination thresholds in the two body locations [17]. By contrast, in the visual domain the Kappa effect increases with the spatial distance, resulting in an average higher Kappa effect on the forearm (although not

significant). Although a precise comparison with previous studies is not straightforward given the different protocols adopted (i.e., regarding the visual channel [3, 4] used only two stimuli equally spaced from the fixation point), also our results suggest a relationship between the distance of the visual stimuli from the retina and the magnitude of the Kappa effect. Considering our results, we speculate that the emergence of the Kappa effect across different perceptual modalities, i.e. the dilation or contraction of time perception through space, could rely on the interplay between the perceptual thresholds across the spatial and the temporal domain. The discrimination thresholds in temporal and spatial domain can account for the magnitude of the Kappa effect, within the Bayesian (maximum likelihood estimation, MLE) optimal integration between vision and touch [12, 29]. Regarding space perception, the visual channel is known to have lower discrimination thresholds than the tactile channel [12]. Regarding the time domain, instead, previous studies [22, 30] found lower discrimination thresholds in the tactile domain ($\sim 160ms$) with respect to the visual domain ($\sim 197ms$) [22]. Finally, in both time and space domains multimodal congruent stimuli gave rise to MLE optimal integration [11, 12].

As noticeable in the comparison between the visual and the tactile modality (see Fig. 4 and the coefficients of GLMM in Table 1) in the Appendix, the lower discrimination thresholds of vision corresponds to an increase in the magnitude of the Kappa effect which is double in the visual domain with respect to the tactile domain. Moreover, in agreement with MLE rules [29, 31], in bimodal conditions the magnitude of the Kappa effect changes according to the modality with lower variance in the spatial domain (i.e., vision). As a matter of fact, whereas the contributions of the incongruent tactile spatial cues in the BIV modality are negligible compared to the BC modality (i.e., the Kappa effect is almost constant), in the BIT modality the equal spatial distances constantly marked by visual stimuli disrupted the Kappa effect, which resulted even lower than in the unimodal tactile condition.

(b) Duration discrimination

In agreement with [22, 32], in the control conditions, with equal spatial distances, the discrimination thresholds found in the modalities involving the tactile channel (i.e., tactile and BC) were lower than those of the unimodal visual modality (see Fig. 6 and 7), confirming both the higher temporal discrimination in the tactile channel and the rules of the MLE. The presence of the Kappa effect (i.e., blue and green boxplots) reduced the differences in the discrimination thresholds between the visual and tactile channels in both the forearm and the palm (i.e. the differences of the JND were not statistically significant). However, such a reduction of difference between the discrimination thresholds did not affect the cross-modal integration in the BC modality: as shown in figures 8 and 9, the relation between discrimination thresholds predicted from unimodal contributions using the MLE rules and the

experimental data collected in the BC modality is not altered by the presence the Kappa effect (i.e., it is independent from the spatial distribution of the stimuli). Interestingly though, predictions are less reliable for participants having higher discrimination thresholds, meaning that the participant showing high discrimination thresholds in unimodal conditions benefit less from redundant information given by the multimodal stimulation in the temporal domain. Speculating, those participants did not perceived the bimodal stimuli as a multimodal representation of a single event, and therefore applied a sort of segregation strategy.

Interestingly, our results show a linear dependency between the ability to discriminate time intervals and the magnitude of the Kappa effect experienced by participant in the different modalities (see 10). To this end, we speculate that the measurement of the duration discrimination threshold of a specific subject can be used as a predictor of the magnitude of Kappa effect.

(c) Limitations

A limitation of this study regards the integration of visual and tactile information provided in the BC modality: although the spatial source and the temporal synchronization of the stimuli were coherent between the perceptual channels, perhaps such information was not perceived as a multimodal evidence of the same event by all the participants. To this end, in future work the experimental protocol can be adapted to virtual reality (VR) environment, where the taps generated by the solenoids can be associated to various visual events, like a flashing light, or the collision of virtual objects bouncing on top of the participants' skin. In VR, we speculate that the tactile stimuli should improve the sense of immersion while supporting the Kappa effect driven by the visual domain.

5. Conclusion

In this work we provided, for the first time, a comprehensive characterization of the Kappa effect in the visual-tactile conditions, within the peripersonal space (i.e., at the palm and the forearm), considering both unimodal and concurrent multimodal elicitations. Although the origin of this perceptual space-time illusion is unknown, the most discussed theories [9, 33] link the effects of time distortion to the violation of a prior knowledge related to a constant apparent movement generated within a sequence of stimuli [33] or to a prior of slowness [9] (i.e., human tend to associate to real-world moving objects a slow speed). To this regard, in future work we plan to evaluate the possible priors underpinning the Kappa effect, by applying a systematic space-time manipulation of virtual objects in both the visual and tactile domain in VR. The effective translation of Kappa Effect in VR, and more in general in extended reality, could be used to design new experimental protocols for manipulating the perception of self in time. This could open to the interesting scenarios of emotion modulation through the parametric tuning of

time perception, thus unlocking a plethora of VR-based activities as well as a number of exploitation avenues in the diagnosis and re-stratification of affective disorders, with the possibility of devising novel therapeutic strategies.

A. Generalized Linear Mixed Modeling

By means of multiple generalized linear mixed model (GLMM), we tested whether the factor space (short, equal, long) affected Kappa effect for each modality and place. GLMM accounts for the effect of the experimental variables and for the variability between participants by means of fixed- and random- effect parameters, respectively [34]. Models were of the form:

$$\Phi^{-1}[P(Y = 1)] = \beta_0 + u_0 + \beta_1 \cdot x + u_1 \cdot x + \beta_2(S) + \beta_3(L) \quad (\text{A } 1)$$

where Φ^{-1} is the probit link function, $P(Y = 1)$ is the probability of perceiving the first stimulus as longer than the second, β_* and u_* are the fixed- and random- effect parameters, respectively. S and L are two dummy variables correspondent to the levels of the factor Space short(S) and long(L).

psychometric function (i.e., $JND = 0.75/\beta_1$). The coefficients β_2 and β_3 are related to the short and long condition, respectively: the PSE of the corresponding psychometric functions can be calculated as $-(\beta_0 + \beta_2)/\beta_1$ and $-(\beta_0 + \beta_3)/\beta_1$. The value of such coefficients, usually specular to zero, changes with modalities in agreement with Fig. 4. For instance, β_2 in the visual modality is twice the tactile modality. Regarding the factor Place, instead, for all the modalities the coefficients are within the range of the SE. In general, the random effect in the models showed a limited variance (0.04 – 0.08) on the intercept, whereas it showed a greater variance on the slope (0.3 – 0.8), meaning that the discrimination thresholds were different among the participants.

We investigated also if the subject-specific effects were correlated with any of the static predictors. In particular, age and arm length values were standardized, and linear models were fitted between such predictors and both random intercepts and slopes. Whereas the coefficients were always not significant, the AIC parameter increased in all the configurations tested, meaning that such parameters were not improving the model fit.

Figure 12: Individual results and psychometric functions calculated with GLMM of duration discrimination task in the visual unimodal modality (forearm)

Tables 1 and 2 report the coefficients of the unimodal and multimodal models, respectively. In agreement with the previous data analysis, for all modalities and places the coefficient β_0 , representing the PSE of control condition, reports values close to zero, therefore always not significant. The coefficient β_1 , significant in all modalities and places, is related to the inverse of standard deviation of the

Figure 13: Individual results and psychometric functions calculated with GLMM of duration discrimination task in the tactile unimodal modality (forearm)

Figure 12 and 13 report the GLMM of the unimodal visual and tactile modalities applied on the experimental data for each participants, respectively. Although the GLMM only provides 3 significant parameters for each factor combination of Modality and Place, it nevertheless allows to represent the Magnitude of the Kappa effect (i.e., the translation of the PSE on the x -axis) and the

JND of most of the participants. However, compared to specific participants which report an unbalanced Kappa effect (e.g., Fig.12 sub1 long, sub9 short, sub 11 short) the psychometric functions individually computed on the experimental data, the GLMM is unable to fit the data of

Ethics. The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the University of Pisa (Prot. n. 36590/2021)

Data Accessibility. Data of the experiments can be found in <https://10.5281/zenodo.7299440>

Authors' Contributions. YDP designed the experimental devices. YDP, VC, and MB designed the experiments, performed the statistical analysis and wrote the article. GV and VVW supervised and supported the design of the experiments. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

Competing Interests. The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Table 1: Coefficients of fixed effects the unimodal models (with SE) Significance levels: *=0.01, **=0.001, ***=0.0001

Modality	Visual		Tactile	
	Palm	Forearm	Palm	Forearm
β_0	0.15 (0.07)	0.01 (0.07)	0.06 (0.06)	0.03 (0.06)
β_1	1.05 (0.18)***	0.92 (0.17)***	1.21 (0.21)***	1.08 (0.14)***
β_2	-0.59 (0.05)***	-0.61 (0.05)***	-0.28 (0.05)***	-0.34 (0.05)***
β_3	0.76 (0.05)***	0.82 (0.05)***	0.40 (0.05)***	0.33 (0.05)***

Table 2: Coefficients of fixed effects the models (with SE) Significance levels: *=0.01, **=0.001, ***=0.0001

Modality	BC		BIV		BIT	
	Palm	Forearm	Palm	Forearm	Palm	Forearm
β_0	0.08 (0.08)	0.00 (0.07)	0.07 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.06)	0.07 (0.08)	-0.01 (0.07)
β_1	1.27 (0.22)***	1.16 (0.20)***	1.24 (0.22)***	1.24 (0.23)***	1.22 (0.23)***	1.16 (0.21)***
β_2	-0.66 (0.05)***	-0.55 (0.05)***	-0.60 (0.05)***	-0.51 (0.05)***	-0.04 (0.05)	-0.12 (0.05)*
β_3	0.74 (0.05)***	0.83 (0.05)***	0.64 (0.05)***	0.80 (0.05)***	0.13 (0.05)**	0.11 (0.05)*

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